

DURABILITY KINETIC MODELING OF CLAY NANO REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE AT LOW TEMPERATURE OXIDATION

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1 General Introduction

A small number of studies dealing with the thermo-oxidation aging kinetics of clay nanofilled polypropylene are available, all of them developed at temperatures higher than 250°C, far above the use temperature interval for the use of polypropylene (PP) (1,2,3). From our knowledge, no studies on the thermo-oxidation mechanisms and kinetics in solid state at moderate temperatures are available in the literature. Scarceness of information regards not only experimental results of the kinetic behavior of polypropylene clay nanocomposites, but also which concerns to a possible application of a general strategy or an analytical methodology for studying degradation of these materials.

Our purpose was to study in an experimental and a theoretical way the thermal oxidation of non stabilized clay polypropylene nanocomposites (NC) at temperatures 60, 80 and 100°C, corresponding to PP practical use. The Closed Loop Model (CLM) (3,4), previously developed in our laboratory, was used for performing the kinetic modeling of the oxidation process and to make predictions of end-product lifetime.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Propilco 01R25 propylene-ethylene copolymer (MFI 0.8 g/10 min) was used as polymer matrix. The nano-clay filler was Nanofil® SE 3000 (Süd Chemie AG) modified montmorillonite. After blending the quantity of organically modified clay present in the nanocomposite was equal to 4.53 % of weight (TGA analysis). The morphologic state of the nanocomposite was characterized by transmission electronic microscopy (TEM) and wide angle x-ray diffraction (WAXS). The nanocomposite presented intercalation/exfoliation morphology. Oxygen permeability tests were then additionally performed and resulted in a 30 % improvement on the

permeability value related to the pure polyolefin due to the clay incorporation. To remove stabilizers, the press molded films (160°C) of 75 and 150 µm were extracted at 60°C and then exposed at 60, 80 and 100±1°C in ventilated ovens to thermal oxidation.

2.1 FTIR analysis

Changes of global carbonyl concentration (mol kg⁻¹) in the films were followed in transmission mode using Bruker IFS 128 spectrophotometer at 1713 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 300 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The carbonyl profiles in 150 µm films were measured with a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Spotlight 300 ATR-FTIR microscope equipped with large germanium crystal with 6 µm spatial resolution.

3 Results

3.1 Characterization of the Oxidation Process

The thermo-oxidation kinetics of PP and nanocomposite films at 60, 80 and 100°C followed by the carbonyl average concentration ($[CO]_{av}$) as a function of time is presented on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Kinetics of the pure polypropylene and the nanocomposite at 60, 80 and 100°C (CLM lines and experimental points).

T (°C)	t _i PP (h)	t _i NC (h)
100	33	25
80	220	150
60	1580	1300

Table 1. Oxidation induction times for the polypropylene and composite films.

Induction time values for both polymers at the three defined temperatures are summarized in Table 1. It appears that the induction time values obtained for the nanocomposite films are lower for all exposure temperatures, indicating that the nanocomposite is slightly more oxidizable. In a first approach, it was necessary to assess the significance of the induction time difference between both materials. For this purpose, we plotted in an Arrhenius diagram the induction times of our PP and our NC with compiled literature data for various non stabilized polypropylenes from sixties to present (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Arrhenius graph for induction times (t_i) for the pure polypropylene and the nanocomposite.

From this coarse grain point of view, it clearly appears that the difference observed in Tab. 1 between pure PP and the nanocomposite is not very significant since all induction period values are situated in the scatter of points corresponding to induction period values reported in the literature. The nanofiller does not influence on the apparent activation energy for induction period values, its average value being close to 116 kJ mol^{-1} . As a result, the nanocomposite can be considered as a pure PP for its oxidation behavior in the first approach.

3.2 Oxygen diffusion controlled oxidation

It is well known that PP oxidation is non homogeneous in the thickness of PP (5) even at mild exposition conditions. To put the oxidation heterogeneity in evidence for materials and conditions under study, carbonyl profiles of oxidized films were determined using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Spotlight 300 ATR-FTIR microscope. It appears clearly that for both materials (Fig. 3, points and triangles) that the oxidation is

heterogeneous after the end of the induction period and that the oxidation kinetics is oxygen diffusion controlled. The thickness of oxidized layer at 100°C was $17 \mu\text{m}$ and for PP and $10 \mu\text{m}$ for the nanocomposite. From our knowledge, it is the first time that an oxidation profile for PP was measured with such accuracy.

Fig. 3. Calculated (CLM) and experimental oxidation profiles for different average carbonyl concentration ($[\text{CO}]_{av}$) a) pure PP, b) NC.

3.3 Oxidation kinetic modeling

The Closed Loop Model (CLM), developed in our laboratory, was used to model oxidation kinetics (4,5,6). This model is derived from a standard mechanistic scheme of hydrocarbon polymers oxidation in which oxidation results from a radical chain reactions initiated by hydroperoxide decomposition. For kinetic modeling of non stabilized clay polypropylene nanocomposite two supplementary factors influencing oxidation kinetics were taken into account: a) changes of oxygen diffusivity D_{O_2} due to nanofiller, and b) a change of initiation rate due to catalytic effect of transition metal impurities M^{n+} (iron particles) on hydroperoxide decomposition (reaction I_{uc}). In this case, the closed-loop mechanistic scheme involves eight elementary reactions giving four differential equations for concentration changes of reaction product including oxygen diffusion process (5):

Initiation (unimolecular (I_u) and (I_{uc}), and bimolecular (I_b))

Propagation

Termination

Oxygen diffusion process

$$\frac{d[O_2]}{dt} = D_{O_2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 [O_2]}{\partial x^2} \right) - k_2 [P^{\bullet}] O_2 + k_6 [PO_2^{\bullet}]^2$$

with D_{O_2} the diffusion coefficient for the PP matrix and for the NC. Assuming that the source of carbonyl group (CO) is the hydroperoxide decomposition, carbonyl concentration $[CO]_{av}$ is written as:

$$\frac{d[CO]_{av}}{dt} = [k_{1uc}[POOH] + k_{1u}[POOH] + k_{1b}[POOH]^2]$$

$$* [1 - X_c - MMT] * \rho_{PP}^{-1}$$

where X_c is the crystallinity ratio of the sample expressed in volume fraction and MMT is the volume fraction of montmorillonite. Materials parameters used in CLM modeling are given in Tab. 2 ($[PH]_0 = 20 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$, $X_c = 0.5$, $S_{O_2} = 1.15 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mol l}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$). The values of kinetic parameters used for PP oxidation modeling by Richaud (5) were completed by the value of catalytic decomposition of POOH k_{uc} and are given as a function of temperature in the Tab. 3. The set of differential equations was resolved using the MATLAB ODS3 software.

	$[POOH]_0$ (mol kg ⁻¹)	MMT	D_{O_2} at 100°C (m ² s ⁻¹)
PP	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$
NC	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.1	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-12}$

Table 2 Material parameters for the CLM for the PP and NC.

Constants	Pre exp. Factor (s ⁻¹ or mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Ea (kJ mol ⁻¹)
k_{1u} (s ⁻¹)	$1.19 \cdot 10^{11}$	135
k_{1uc} (s ⁻¹)	$2.50 \cdot 10^{11}$	120
k_{1b} (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$5.42 \cdot 10^7$	84
k_2 (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$5.38 \cdot 10^7$	5
k_3 (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$9.80 \cdot 10^7$	60
k_4 (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$9.74 \cdot 10^9$	0
k_5 (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$2.66 \cdot 10^9$	0
k_6 (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$7.94 \cdot 10^9$	60

Table 3. Kinetic constants of the CLM for the PP and NC.

A cross checking of theoretical and experimental results was done good agreement as well as for thin films oxidation kinetics (Fig 1, full lines) as for the oxidation profiles (Fig. 3, full lines) both in PP and NC. The oxidation profile difference between PP and its nanocomposite can be attributed principally to oxygen diffusion coefficient difference. In our case (MTT quality) the catalytic decomposition of POOH plays a minor role.

4. Conclusion

It was established that even though the addition of montmorillonite slightly reduces the oxygen permeability of the polyolefin matrix, it does not considerably modify the polypropylene kinetic behaviour under the studied conditions. The CLM is valid for PP based nanocomposite (NC) and can be used for extrapolation of polymer properties changes to low temperatures and durability estimation using an appropriate lifetime criterion as for instance a given carbonyl concentration or better the critical molar weight M_c or with linked mechanical properties (7).

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